

Polypyrrole Nanoparticles Suspended on Graphene for the Detection of Simulant Chemical Warfare Agents

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Abstract— This study develops a gas sensor based on graphene decorated with polypyrrole (PPy) nanoparticles (NPs) for the detection of dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP), a chemical warfare agent simulant. The PPy nanoparticles were synthesized via chemical polymerization with an average diameter of 110 nm and randomly distributed onto exfoliated graphene. The nanomaterials were characterized using field emission scanning electron microscopy, confirming the successful decoration of PPy nanoparticles on the graphene surface. The gas sensing performance of the sensor was evaluated at ambient temperature, demonstrating high stability and reversible interaction with DMMP. The sensor exhibited a linear response to several concentrations of DMMP, with a sensitivity of 14.2% per ppm. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were found to be 171 and 572 ppb, respectively, revealing the sensor's capability to detect trace levels of DMMP. The excellent sensing performance can be attributed to the synergistic effect between both p-type nanomaterials, graphene and PPy. Graphene facilitating fast and efficient charge transfer as transduction element while PPy NPs providing noteworthy reactivity with DMMP by means of hydrogen bonding. Overall, the graphene-PPy nanocomposite sensor shows great potential for the sensitive trace level detection of DMMP in real-world applications.

Index Terms— Chemical Warfare Agents, DMMP, Gas Sensor, Graphene, Polypyrrole

I. INTRODUCTION

Gas sensors play a crucial role in monitoring air pollutants, especially highly dangerous compounds. There are many types of toxic air pollutants, but chemical warfare agents (CWA) pose the greatest potential threat to human health, capable of inducing death even with short-term exposure [1]. Therefore, the detection and identification of these CWA are of paramount importance in security and defense applications. Among the different CWA compounds, nerve agents like Sarin, Soman, and Tabun have fatal effects on human health due to their interference with nerve impulse transmission. Hence, this study focuses on sensing dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP), which typically serves as a simulant for the highly toxic nerve agent Sarin [2].

However, effective monitoring of toxic gases requires extensive sensing networks with geographically distributed nodes. Thereby, the development of inexpensive, durable, and low-power consumption devices is crucial for achieving wide spatial coverage of sensing nodes [3]. In this context, chemical resistive gas sensors have attracted considerable research interest due to their compelling advantages, including cost-effectiveness, user-friendliness, ease of interpretation, and potential for miniaturization. These sensors provide a promising avenue for the development of reliable and efficient gas detection systems [4]. However, the choice of nanomaterial type is crucial to achieving these objectives.

This work focuses on the use of graphene, a nanomaterial with exceptional electrical, mechanical, and chemical properties for gas

sensing purposes. One of the main advantages of graphene is its ability to operate at room temperature, leading to inexpensive, durable, and low-power consumption devices [5]. However, the main limitation of using bare graphene is its reduced sensitivity. To overcome this limitation, a strategic approach has been adopted to enhance the sensitivity of graphene-based gas sensors. Specifically, this study reports the use of polypyrrole (PPy) nanoparticles (NPs) for decorating the graphene layers. PPy is a conductive polymer well-known for its exceptional gas sensing properties, and the use of PPy NPs holds great potential in enhancing the sensing performance, particularly sensitivity [6].

For instance, Z. Yang et al. employed reduced graphene oxide (rGO) decorated with PPy NPs to detect DMMP, demonstrating that the presence of the polymer enhances the response up to 3 times [7]. Similarly, S. Lama et al. developed a quartz crystal microbalance sensor composed of manganese oxide nitrogen-doped graphene oxide (GO) decorated with polypyrrole for enhanced detection of DMMP [8]. However, this work reports, for the first time, the detection of DMMP using pristine graphene, instead of GO or rGO, decorated with PPy NPs synthesized through an easy and industrially scalable process. The use of pristine graphene significantly reduces the cost and complexity of developing the resulting nanomaterial. Moreover, this investigation focuses on achieving the detection of the lowest DMMP concentrations using graphene-based devices decorated with PPy NPs. This achievement is likely due to the utilization of PPy NPs with the smallest average size, a crucial parameter for increasing the surface-to-volume ratio, which plays an essential role in sensing

performance. Thus, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the design and fabrication of cost-effective and reliable gas sensing devices.

II. DESIGN AND METHODS

A. Synthesis of Graphene decorated with PPy NPs

The synthesis of polypyrrole nanoparticles and their use for decorating graphene was carried out following one of our proposed methods [9]. Firstly, a 7.5 wt% solution of poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) in distilled water was prepared under magnetic stirring. Subsequently, iron chloride (FeCl_3) was added to the PVA solution, resulting in the formation of an orange solution. Finally, the pyrrole monomer was added dropwise to the solution, which was stirred overnight to complete the polymerization process. The resulting black-colored nanoparticles were extracted and cleaned through multiple centrifugation steps, followed by washing with distilled water. The obtained polypyrrole nanoparticles were then dried in an oven.

Simultaneously, a graphene solution was prepared by dispersing graphene nanoflakes in distilled water. The solution underwent ultrasonic treatment to achieve suitable graphene exfoliation. Next, 5% wt of polypyrrole nanoparticles were added to the graphene solution and mixed under stirring for 2 hours. This approach involved supporting the polypyrrole nanoparticles on liquid-phase exfoliated graphene, providing an inexpensive, simple, and rapid method for obtaining graphene nanocomposites with suitable decoration.

B. Gas sensing system

The gas sensing system for generating known concentrations of DMMP consists of a combination of two flow lines. The first line uses a mass flow controller to regulate synthetic air with high purity. The second line also uses synthetic air, but in this case, the air passes through a DMMP permeation system consisting of a stainless-steel tube covered with a heated belt. The temperature inside the tube is regulated by a PID controller (proportional integral derivative). In this second line, after the permeation tube, there is another controller to regulate the injected flow. Finally, both gas lines are mixed and connected.

The sensors are placed in a Teflon airtight sensing chamber, enabling the introduction of the generated gas mixture. The changes in resistance are monitored using an Agilent HP 34972A multimeter. Importantly, the DMMP concentration can be adjusted by regulating the temperature and flow rate of the system.

III. Results and discussion

A. Nanomaterial characterization

The obtained nanomaterials were characterized using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM). Fig. 1 shows the isolated PPy NPs, revealing their regular shape and homogeneous size of approximately 110 nm in diameter. Subsequently, these NPs were suspended on graphene, as shown in Fig. 2. The graphene exhibits a porous surface with noticeable roughness, which is beneficial from a gas sensing perspective. Moreover, the PPy NPs are randomly distributed among the graphene, indicating a suitable decoration process.

Fig. 1. FESEM image of the polypyrrole nanoparticles synthesized.

Fig. 2. FESEM image showing the graphene decorated with PPy NPs. The blue squares pretend to highlight some NPs grafted on the graphene surface.

B. DMMP Detection

The sensing performance of graphene decorated with PPy NPs for detecting DMMP was studied at ambient temperature, which allows for limited power consumption and eliminates the need for heating elements; thereby reducing production costs. Four different concentrations of DMMP (0.6, 1.1, 1.6, and 2.1 ppm) were applied for 5 minutes. These concentrations can be generated by regulating the temperature of the permeation tube containing this CWA simulant. Fig. 3 illustrates an example of the resistance changes observed when exposing the sensitive films to 5 minutes of DMMP. Each gas exposure was followed by 15 minutes of synthetic air to recover the resistance baseline. The Fig. 1 demonstrates the high stability of the sensor, even when operated at room temperature. The original baseline resistance was practically recovered after 15 minutes of air, indicating high sensor stability and reversible interaction with DMMP.

Fig. 3. Electrical responses obtained when detecting trace levels of DMMP with graphene decorated with PPy NPs.

These outstanding parameters would result in a sensor with an extended lifetime, absence of baseline drift, excellent signal-to-noise ratio, and noteworthy repeatability. By considering the changes in resistance, the sensor response for each DMMP concentration was calculated using the following formula:

$$Response (\%) = \frac{R_f - R_0}{R_0} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where R_0 is the resistance value under synthetic air, and R_f corresponds to the resistance under the target gas. In this case, DMMP is a well-known electron donor molecule, and when it interacts with a p-type sensitive film, it increases the resistance. This decrease in conductivity is due to the fact that positive carriers (holes) in p-type semiconductors are the majority carriers. Thus, when DMMP interacts with the sensor, it transfers negative carriers (electrons), resulting in a decrease in the density of majority carriers.

Fig. 4 depicts the calibration curve obtained based on the different responses corresponding to the DMMP concentration. A linear response ($R^2 = 0.9907$) can be observed. Furthermore, the sensor sensitivity, which is usually given by the slope of the calibration curve, reveals a noteworthy sensitivity of 14.2% per ppm. This suggests that the developed sensitive film is capable of reliably detecting DMMP in the parts per billion (ppb) range. It is worth noting that the lowest concentration tested was 600 ppb. To assess the possibility of detecting trace levels of this gas, the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were calculated using the following formulas:

$$LOD = \frac{3S_a}{b} \quad (2)$$

$$LOQ = \frac{10S_a}{b} \quad (3)$$

where S_a corresponds to the standard deviation of the y-intercepts, and b is the slope of the experimental calibration curve. As a result, the LOD and LOQ are theoretically 171 and 572 ppb, respectively.

Fig. 4. Calibration curve for DMMP detection, ranging from 0.6 to 2.1 ppm.

These values are significantly lower than those reported in most similar works. Table 1 summarizes the sensing performance of graphene-based gas sensors operated under similar experimental conditions, such as room temperature detection. The PPy NPs suspended on graphene shows high potential for detecting trace levels of DMMP in real-world settings.

Table 1. Comparison of DMMP sensing performance employing different resistive graphene-based gas sensors and operated at ambient temperature.

Material	Response / ppm	Exposure time (s)
PPy -Graphene ^a	22.6 % / 2.1 ppm	300
PPy NPs - rGO [7]	12.9 % / 100 ppm	43
Cu ^{x+} - PPy - rGO [10]	10.4 % / 100 ppm	49
Graphene [11]	8.95 % / 50 ppm	240
Functionalized MWCNTs [12]	0.8 % / 100 ppm	30

^aThis work

C. Gas sensing mechanism

Both nanomaterials comprising the nanohybrid exhibit mild p-type behavior. Although graphene theoretically has zero bandgap, the presence of structural defects in the carbon lattice and the oxygen functional species grafted on its surface make graphene behave as a p-type semiconductor [13]. Similarly, PPy NPs exhibit the same behavior, as emphasized by the chosen synthesis route. Previous studies have reported that the produced PPy NPs are positively charged (PPy⁺) due to Cl⁻ doping [14]. Thus, under room temperature measurements, when the electron-donor DMMP gas interacts with the sensitive layer, a charge transfer occurs, reducing the number of holes.

The remarkable sensing performance can be attributed to several factors. DMMP can directly interact with the defects in graphene or with the oxygen species grafted on its surface [15]. However, bare graphene usually exhibits limited sensitivity and reactivity. For this reason, the main contribution to the sensitivity can be attributed to the presence of PPy NPs, which are significantly more reactive than graphene [16]. Since the measurements were conducted at ambient temperature, the adsorption of DMMP on the sensitive film likely occurs through hydrogen bonds [7]. Previous studies have demonstrated that the P=O bonds of DMMP tend to interact with the N-H bonds of PPy [17]. Therefore, the formation of hydrogen bonds enables the sensitive detection of DMMP, resulting in low LOD and LOQ values. Moreover, the adsorption of the analyte on the sensitive layer is weak, as evidenced by the fast recovery of the resistance baseline without the need for applying heat or UV light to break the hydrogen bonds. This is in agreement with previous works reporting that 15 minutes of synthetic air is sufficient to completely remove the adsorbed DMMP from the surface [7].

The combination of graphene and PPy can potentially exhibit a synergistic effect that improves the sensing performance. The high electron mobility of graphene enables efficient and fast charge transfer with the PPy NPs, resulting in a functional transduction mechanism between both nanomaterials. Furthermore, the highly porous graphene surface facilitates and accelerates the sensing response through efficient diffusion of DMMP molecules [18].

IV. CONCLUSION

Graphene decorated with PPy NPs has been demonstrated as a suitable option to detect simulant nerve agents such as DMMP. The sensing performance of the sensitive layer demonstrated high stability, reversibility, and sensitivity to DMMP under room temperature measurements. Thereby, this hybrid can pave the way toward low-powered gas sensors.

Besides, the results obtained outperform previous graphene-based gas sensors and highlight the potential of the developed sensor for real-world applications. But not limited to this, future research can focus on further enhancing the sensing performance, expanding the range of target analytes, and exploring the sensor's applicability in different environmental conditions.

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